

NCS 2041, NCS 2043, NCS 2044, NCS 2046, NCS 2048, NCS 2049, NCS 2055, NCS 2057, NCS 2072, NCS 2107, and Palman 579. Lesion lengths ranged from 2.2 cm to 3.6 cm. Some cultivars were susceptible as seedlings but resistant at adult stage — ARC 5913, ARC 5938, ARC 5951, ARC 6248, ARC 10602, ARC 11281, Denga Faram, IR2035-117-3, IR15705-199-3-3, Jhina, Jikkoku/Serpheke chil 52-102, Mudgo, NCS 320, NCS 332, NCS 338, NCS 335, NCS 2015, NCS 2018, Sinna Sivappu, T 1426, Vallathil Cheera, and Vellai Langayan. Disease scores ranged from 2.2 to 3.8. ■

Disease reaction of some rice stocks at seedling and at adult plant stage at Punjab, India.

Stock or cultivar	Source	Lesion length (cm) at seedling stage		Scores at adult stage (0-9 scale)
		Mean	Range	
MTU15/Waiseakokku-127	CRR1	3.65	2.0-7.0	2.7
ARC6044	CRR1	3.75	2.5-5.0	4.0
ARC11321	CRR1	3.68	2.0-6.0	3.4
ARC11367	CRR1	2.75	2.0-4.5	2.2
IET6123	CRR1	3.40	2.5-4.5	3.4
NCS2001	CRR1	3.50	1.5-5.0	3.0
NCS2009	CRR1	1.43	0.5-2.5	3.2
NCS2039	CRR1	2.48	2.0-3.5	3.7
NCS1604	CRR1	3.98	2.0-8.0	3.4
Kogyoku (<i>Xa 1</i>)	IRRI	1.50	1.0-2.0	0.8
Tetep (<i>Xa 1 + Xa 2</i>)	IRRI	1.20	0.5-2.5	1.4
Wau Qikoku-3 (<i>Xa 3</i>)	IRRI	2.23	1.0-4.5	1.7
IR1545-339 (<i>xa 5</i>)	IRRI	2.95	2.0-4.5	1.3
IR20 (<i>Xa 4</i>)	IRRI	4.78	3.0-7.0	5.6
TN1 (susceptible check)		16.68	8.5-26.5	6.5

Bacterial blight resistance under natural conditions

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During the 1980 and 1981 wet seasons, bacterial blight appeared in epidemic form in several pockets of the Chhatisgarh region. During the high natural infection in 1981, germplasm accessions of early and medium duration were screened for resistance, using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.

Of 6,129 cultivars screened, only 1 scored 1, 24 scored 3, and the others 5-9

(Table 1). No seed could be harvested from several highly susceptible lines. No very early variety was resistant.

The 25 cultivars with scores of 1 and 3 (Table 2) have been selected for further tests under artificial inoculation. They have also been crossed with varieties carrying known resistance genes to study their allelic relationship. ■

Table 1. Resistance of germplasm accessions of rice of different maturities for natural bacterial blight epidemic in Raipur, M.P. India.

Maturity group	Accessions screened (no.)	Accessions (no.) with given bacterial blight resistance ^a score				
		1	3	5	7	9
Extra early (up to 90 days)	558	0	0	14	122	422
Very early (91 to 110 days)	496	0	3	57	138	298
Early (111 to 125 days)	2313	1	11	205	833	1263
Medium (126 to 140 days)	2762	0	10	744	1058	950
Total	6129	1	24	1020	2151	2933

^aStandard Evaluation System for Rice, % hills affected: 1 = less than 1%, 3 = 1-5%, 5 = 6-25%, 7 = 26-50%, 9 = 51-100%.

Table 2. Bacterial blight-resistant varieties at Raipur, M.P., India.

Karhani	Kechana
Benikath	Khuraban
Bhatapyagi	Liktimati
Badshahbhog	Ruingi
Bhatagunda	Rotad
Chingerchopa	Rageem 14
Chinee Kapoor	Safed jeera
Dilbaksa	Sataka
Gotaka	SLO
Jalkesar	Tikurdhan
Kesariya	Vishnubhog
Kosma	X 11
Kariyakora	

Varietal reaction to natural infection of rice tungro virus in Bihar

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Rice tungro virus infection under natural conditions was very high during 1980-81 kharif. The disease appeared the first week of August in transplanted Taichung Native 1 in a dryland field and

Table 1. Varietal reaction to rice tungro virus at Bihar, India.

Resistance score ^a	Released varieties	Promising varieties
3	Pusa 2-21, CR44-35 (Saket 4) Ratna, BR34, Janaki (64-117), BR9, Katarni, IR20	Pusa 33, TCA4, TCA177
5	Rajendra Dhan 201	TCA80-4, IET6263, RP1045-403-1
7	Rasi (IET1444), BR14, BR8, Type 3, Pankaj, Sita, PR106	BIET927, BIET1107, IET5656, ET5882, FH132
9	Jaya, IR8, Mahsuri, BR46, Prasad, Bala, Cauvery, NC1626, Improved Sona	UPR82-1-7, IET6155, BIET724, BG90-2, TCA62-68, TCA62-10, BIET1048, BIET821, IET2707, CRMS37, IET5883, IET5890, IET6314, IET5897, IET6212

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 0-9: 3 = 6-10% incidence, 9 = 81-100%.